

Synthesis and Condensation of 1-chloro-3,4-dihydro-4-oxopyridazino(4,5-b)indoles with 2-Aminothiazoles and Hydrazine

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2-Carboethoxyindole-3-carboxaldehyde (1a and b) gave 3,4-dihydro-4-oxopyridazino(4,5-b)indole (2a and b) when refluxed with equimolar amount of $N_2H_4.H_2O$ in ethanol. 2a and b yielded 1-chloro-3,4-dihydro-4-oxopyridazino(4,5-b)indole (4a and b) and not 4-chloropyridazino(4,5-b)indole (3a and b) when treated with $POCl_3$ and PCl_5 . 4a and b were condensed with 2-aminothiazoles and $N_2H_4.H_2O$ to get 1-amino(2-thiazolyl)- and 1-hydrazino-3,4-dihydro-4-oxopyridazino(4,5-b)indoles (6aa'-d'), 6ba'-d' and 5a and b, respectively. Some of these compounds showed moderate antimicrobial activity.

It was established by Suvorov and coworkers¹ that 2-carboethoxyindole-3-carboxaldehyde on reaction with hydrazine hydrate under different conditions yielded different products. In view of this we proposed to prepare various Bz-substituted 4-chloropyridazino(4,5-b)indoles and to condense them with different aminothiazoles² with an object of obtaining active antimicrobial products.

5-Methyl-2-carboethoxy-7-bromoindole-3-carboxaldehyde (1a) was refluxed in ethanol with equimolar quantity of hydrazine hydrate. The ir spectrum of the product displayed characteristic bands at 3265 and 1700 cm^{-1} due to NH stretching and C=O of cyclic imide, respectively. Hence the structure 8-methyl-6-bromo-3,4-dihydro-4-oxopyridazino(4,5-b)indole (2a) was given to it. 2a was unaffected on refluxing with excess of $POCl_3$ or with $POCl_3$ and nitrobenzene. However, on reaction with equimolar quantity of PCl_5 and $POCl_3$ a product (m.p. 163-5°) was isolated. Its ir spectrum exhibited a band at 3175 cm^{-1} attributable to NH. It was surprising to note a band at 1710 cm^{-1} which indicated that the cyclic imide moiety in the molecule was intact. It also meant that 2a had imide character and C=O group did not enolise to give OH function which could then be replaced by Cl. Thus the structure 3a was ruled out and a structure 8-methyl-1-chloro-6-bromo-3,4-dihydro-4-oxopyridazino(4,5-b)indole (4a) given to it. Its nmr spectrum ($CDCl_3$) expressed in δ ppm showed five distinct singlets. A peak at 9.45 was due to indole NH while the one at 8.22 due to imide NH. Two singlets at 7.4 and 7.28 were assigned to two aromatic protons 7-H and 9-H, respectively. The 8-methyl group resonated at 2.5. The mass spectrum also confirmed the structure. It showed molecular ion peak at m/e 311. Isotopic peaks at m/e 313 and 315 appeared due to the presence of one chlorine and one bromine atom in the molecule. These M,

M+2 and M+4 peaks were in the ratio as required by theory³. The mass spectrum was as follows: m/e 311, 313, 315 (M, M+2, M+4; 20.83, 27.08, 9.72%); m/e 268, 270, 272 (M-43, M+2-43, M+4-43; 75.68, 100, 26.38%); m/e 190, 192 (M-121, M+2-121; 24.31, 8.68%).

TABLE 1—3,4-DIHYDRO-4-OXOPYRIDAZINO(4,5-b)INDOLES

Compound	m.p. °C	Nature (solvent)	Found%			Molecular Formula	Calcd. %		
			C	H	N		C	H	N
<u>2a</u>	316	Yellow needles (dioxane)	47.22	3.10	14.89	C ₁₁ H ₈ ON ₂ Br	47.49	2.88	15.11
<u>2b</u>	310	"	68.08	4.44	21.00	C ₁₁ H ₈ ON ₂	67.87	4.52	21.10
<u>4a</u>	163-5	Light yellow needles (methanol)	41.98	2.01	13.65	C ₁₁ H ₇ ON ₂ ClBr	42.24	2.24	13.44
<u>4b</u>	132-4	Dark yellow needles (methanol)	56.28	3.71	16.81	C ₁₁ H ₈ ON ₂ Cl	56.53	3.43	17.18

All the compounds were obtained in 70-75% yields.

TABLE 2—1-AMINO(2-THIAZOLYL)- AND 1-HYDRAZINO-3,4-DIHYDRO-4-OXOPYRIDAZINO(4,5-b)INDOLES

Compound	m.p. °C	Nature (solvent)	Found%			Molecular Formula	Calcd. %		
			C	H	N		C	H	N
<u>6aa'</u>	310	Yellow needles (ethanol)	54.21	3.25	15.70	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ ON ₂ BrS	54.34	3.10	15.49
<u>6ab'</u>	225-7	Pink needles (ethanol)	48.75	3.72	16.61	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ ON ₂ BrS	48.79	3.82	16.74
<u>6ac'</u>	310	Yellow needles (ethanol)	46.81	3.81	14.89	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ BrS	46.77	3.46	15.16
<u>6ad'</u>	310	Brownish yellow needles (ethanol)	51.61	4.02	16.40	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ ON ₂ BrS	51.40	3.72	16.31
<u>5a</u>	300	Pale yellow flakes (ethanol)	44.71	3.03	22.85	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ON ₂ BrS	44.43	2.94	23.02
<u>6ba'</u>	300	Yellowish brown needles (ethanol)	65.91	4.05	18.82	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ ON ₂ S	65.85	4.02	18.77
<u>6bb'</u>	300	Reddish yellow needles (dioxane)	60.21	5.18	20.81	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ ON ₂ S	60.17	5.01	20.65
<u>6bc'</u>	300	Dark brown needles (methanol)	56.88	4.45	18.29	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S	56.40	4.44	18.28
<u>6bd'</u>	190	Orange needles (dioxane)	61.37	4.62	19.81	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ ON ₂ S	61.55	4.84	19.95
<u>5b</u>	300	Brownish needles (dioxane)	50.51	4.39	26.28	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ON ₂ S	50.58	4.22	26.82

All the compounds were obtained in 60-80% yields.

4a was condensed with four different 2-aminothiazoles, viz., 2-amino-4-phenyl-, 4-ethyl-5-methyl-, 4-ethyl-5-carbethoxy-, 4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzothiazoles and hydrazine hydrate in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate in ethanol to obtain 8-methyl-1-amino (4'-phenyl-2'-thiazolyl)-6-bromo-3,4-dihydro-4-oxo-, 8-methyl-1-amino(4'-ethyl-5'-methyl-2'-thiazolyl)-6-bromo-3,4-dihydro-4-oxo-, 8-methyl-1-amino(4'-methyl-5'-carbethoxy-2'-thiazolyl)-6-bromo-3,4-dihydro-4-oxo-, 8-methyl-1-amino(4',5',6',7'-tetrahydro-2'-benzothiazolyl)-6-bromo-3,4-dihydro-4-oxo- and 8-methyl-1-hydrazino-6-bromo-3,4-dihydro-4-oxopyridazino(4,5-b)indoles (6aa', 6ab', 6ac', 6ad' and 5a), respectively. All these condensation products showed a carbonyl absorption band around 1700 cm⁻¹ in ir spectrum.

Similarly, 2b was obtained from 1b and hydrazine hydrate. It was chlorinated at position 1 to get 4b which was then condensed with the above four aminothiazoles and hydrazine hydrate to get the condensed products 6ba'-d' and 5e. The nmr and mass spectra of 4, 5 and 6 are in agreement with the structures assigned.

Antimicrobial activity: The compound 4a showed moderate activity against yeast but no activity against *S.aureus* and *E.coli*, 6aa' was moderately active against all three microorganisms. No

other pyridazinoindoles showed antimicrobial activity. The testing was carried out by cup-plate agar diffusion method.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 257 spectrometer in nujol. NMR spectrum was run in CDCl₃ on Varian XL 100 instrument using TMS as internal standard. Chemical shifts are expressed in δ ppm.

3,4-Dihydro-4-oxopyridazino(4,5-b)indoles (2a and b): 2-Carbethoxyindole-3-carboxaldehyde (1a and b) (0.02 mole) was dissolved in ethanol (80 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (0.025 mole, 80%) added. The solution was heated under reflux for 4 hr. The separated yellow solid was filtered, washed with hot ethanol (10 ml) and crystallised from dioxane to give 2a and b (Table 1).

1-Chloro-3,4-dihydro-4-oxopyridazino(4,5-b)indoles (4a and b): 4a and b (0.015 mole) was intimately mixed with PCI₅ (3.13 g, 0.015 mole) and freshly distilled POCl₃ (40 ml) added. The mixture was refluxed until a clear solution obtained (1 hr), cooled and slowly decomposed over crushed ice (500 g) and filtered. The residue was washed with

water, dried and crystallised from methanol to get 4a and b (Table 1).

1-Amino(2-thiazolyl)- and 1-hydrazino-3,4-dihydro-4-oxopyridazino(4,5-b)indoles (6aa'-d', 5a-b): 4a and b (0.001 mole) was dissolved in ethanol (15 ml) to which potassium carbonate (1 g) and the appropriate 2-aminothiazole or hydrazine hydrate (0.001 mole) was added. The mixture was heated under reflux for 4 hr. It was then filtered, the residual potassium carbonate washed with ethanol (5 ml) and the filtrate evaporated to get a solid product which was crystallised from a suitable solvent to obtain (6aa'-d' and 5a-b) (Table 2).

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